

Electrical & Computer Engineering: An International Journal (ECIJ)

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Call for papers

Electrical & Computer Engineering: An International Journal (ECIJ) is a peer-reviewed, open access journal that address the impacts and challenges of Electrical and Computer Engineering. The journal documents practical and theoretical results which make a fundamental contribution for the development Electrical and Computer Engineering.

Topics of interest include, but are not limited to, the following

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- Control, Intelligent Systems and Robotics
- Integrated Circuits and Embedded Systems
- Microelectronic Technologies, Devices, CAD and, VLSI
- Microwave, Nano Devices and RF
- Power and Energy Systems
- Signal Processing and New Media
- Applied Electromagnetics
- Artificial Intelligence and Artificial Life
- Hardware Formal Verification
- Photonics
- Software Engineering and Real-time Systems

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail: ecijjournal@wireilla.com or through [Submission System](#). Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline: September 05, 2020**
- Notification: September 29, 2020
- Final Manuscript Due: October 07, 2020
- Publication Date: Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

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